

Politics And The Crisis Of Development In 21st Century Africa: A Study Of Nigeria's 4th Republic

Isaac Imouhera Azenabor

Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Ambrose Alli University,
Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

isaacazenabor@aauekpoma.edu.ng

Charles Sikibo Ijuyedagogo(PhD)

University of Port Harcourt River
State, Nigeria.

dr.charlesijuye_dagogo@yahoo.com

&

Akinola Awodeyi-Akinsehinwa (PhD)

University of Port Harcourt River
State, Nigeria

Akinolakin001@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Much of contemporary Africa is replete with under-development. Though previous and extant attempts to address this condition have failed (perhaps because either they lack outright efficacy to achieve the desired results or due to human factors), still, the undesirable condition needs to be reversed. Civilized society desires order, evolves a structure incorporating both individual freedom and a clear set of rules for interpersonal relationships. Similarly, civilized society appreciates the need for a characteristic and effective set of principles for assigning basic rights, duties, and burdens of social cooperation amid responsibility. And the adequacy or otherwise of such principles has corresponding effect on development. With the lacunae in Nigeria's Fourth Republic in focus and adopting the Institutional and the Developing State Theories, this paper adopted some qualitative methodology and analyzed the issues about development (in its modern sense) and its lack in contemporary Africa. Accordingly, the work indicated that development would elope the continent of Africa because contemporary politicking and governance (from the experience in Nigeria's 4th Republic) is marred by corruption. The work however suggests practical routes out of the conundrum. **Keywords:** Africa, development, Nigeria/4th republic, politics

INTRODUCTION

Injustice and corruption are a serious bane of development in Africa. Yet one of the most or foremost virtues of the individual, society, and institutions is justice or the idea of justice. This is because every society desires order and thus evolves a system or structure which incorporates both individual freedom and a fair distribution of goods and other interpersonal relationships. In other words, civilized society appreciates the need for (and is always prepared to affirm) a characteristic set of principles to adopt for assigning basic rights and duties, and for determining the criteria to adopt for fair and proper distribution of benefits and burdens of social cooperation. It could be indicated that the adequacy or otherwise of such principles has corresponding effect on development. Accountability is necessary for principles to be effective. Perhaps this is why public officials are required to swear to some oath of allegiance as a premise for social responsibility. Accordingly, it shall be argued that an efficacious oath system along with social, moral, legal, and individual responsibility and accountability are necessary to achieve justice, peace, and development in society—particularly the African society. We shall proceed by discussing alternative conceptions of justice, development, oath-taking and accountability, and thereafter indicate their interrelationships.

Certainly, most Third World countries are naturally endowed in both material and human resources; yet, pathetically, some of these countries are so underdeveloped despite this natural resources advantage. The plundering of the resources of these countries during colonialism has largely been responsible for this present situation. Even though some of the countries in the Third World have found their path to development, others (mainly African) have not. There abound a number of factors deduced to the present condition of Africa which might be termed as development crisis—since the continent has remained largely underdeveloped regardless of the presence of huge natural resources (gold, cocoa, bauxite, oil, diamond, timber) amid abundant human resource-presence. For instance, several decades after the end of colonialism, most parts of Africa is still fighting with problems such as high poverty rate, corruption, lack of basic infrastructural facilities in all sectors of the economy, unemployment, high mortality rate, political instability and insecurity of lives and property. The discourse on development issues is very topical. It is impossible to talk about development without referring to concepts such as poverty, production, the notion of the state, or equality. These concepts initially became prominent since early modernity/Western history; and only then have they (issues about development) been projected on the rest of the world (Sachs, 1992, 5). For example, Ghana touted as one of the best democratic and politically stable countries in Africa and Nigeria the most heavily populated African country, according to the United Nations Human Development Report in 2011, ranked 135 and 156 respectively out of 187 countries (UN, 2011). However, and against the backdrop of Africa's developmental crisis, there has been a surge in the discourse on how to initiate positive policies/programmes. This debate is, perhaps, a blistering one; and it is dominated by two main related themes, namely: the argument over the actual meaning of the concept of development and the appropriate pathway to development (Ikenna, 2009). However, despite the multi-dimensional or divergent approaches among (local and international scholars, global policy makers and institutions over these issues), they are numerous attempts have been made to understand and solve the crisis of development in Africa.

Accordingly, this paper aims to examine the nature of and issues about development/underdevelopment in general and to examine the factors responsible for the

lingering underdevelopment in Africa with special focus on Nigeria. We shall therefore review the performance of politics in contemporary Nigeria (as an instance for contemporary African states). The work shall articulate the nature, adequacy or otherwise of principles of politics on development based on the experience in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. It shall also suggest possible pathways for the realization of development in the African continent.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Politics

This relates to the (nature or acquisition of) power and those who control its distribution/exercise in the society/state concerned. Politics portends the prior existence of established political organizations and governmental institutions. Politics have to do with power relations in a social/public context. Hence in contemporary times, nations' political activities drive both all national activity and international relations. Popular description holds that politics involves citizens' activities in getting what, when, and how.

Development

By *development* is meant to include the human and material improvements in the various African states. Development is entailed in material/physical structures; it also implies economic growth, increased welfare, and human enhancement; it entails modernization, dialectical transformation and capacity building. But while Willis (2005) considers it essentially in modernity and progress, Peet and Hartwick (1999) think it in terms of improvement in standard of living by the poor. Similarly, Todaro (2011) considers development in material sense at the level of production output reflected in improved GDP. Thus the exact meaning of development has been one of controversy. Thus, the term, development is used in variety of ways. In its traditional application, the term is often equated with growth in per capita income. But development scholars and development agencies (such as the World Bank, IMF, etc.) have since the 1970s, other indicators of development have become widely used by The meeting of basic needs (or, equivalently, reduction in absolute poverty), the creation of modern employment opportunities, and the achievement of a less unequal distribution of income have all become important criteria in determining level of development (Todaro & Smith, 2003). Moreover, development "development must therefore be conceived of as a multidimensional process involving major changes in social structures, popular attitudes, and national institutions, as well as the acceleration of economic growth, the reduction of inequality and the eradication of poverty" (Todaro and Smith, 2012, 16). Their position presupposes that development is not purely an economic phenomenon but rather a multi-dimensional process involving reorganization and reorientation of entire economic and social system and is a process of improving the quality of all human lives with some equally important aspects (serving basic components or core values, serving as a conceptual basis and practical guideline for comprehending the inner meaning of development). Nevertheless the core values are sustenance, self-esteem and freedom—which represent universal goal sought after by individual and society (Todaro and Smith, 2012, 16).

On his part, Sen (1999) describes development strictly as converse to that of economic point of view. According to him, all individuals are gifted with certain set of capabilities while it is simply a matter of realizing these capabilities that will allow a person to escape from poverty and achieve freedom—illiteracy, poor health, malnutrition, amongst others, are a few indicators of its lack. Sen further expands the critical interpretations of freedom by examining five

elemental forms of instrumental freedoms: political freedoms, economic facilities, social opportunities, transparency guarantee, and protective security and lays emphasis on the fact that, the five forms of freedom are complementary, interrelated and inextricable. In this way, his presupposes that individual freedom must comprise of the five for an individual to realize his or her potentials. Further, development implies advancement and growth in any organized state, both in quantitative and qualitative terms: establishment of structures, building of attitudes, institutions—economic, social, political, religious, and legal.

Development is positive in nature. In some sense, development implies a comparative state of affairs: between past state of the same society, or between two or more societies—a matter of per capita income. Specifically, development is also a strategy of spatial reorganization crucial for the whole process of political mobilization and central state control of the planning of productive forces, not necessarily centralized at just a point. This means that development is the exploitation of nature, education, human capacity for social upliftment. Human development connotes enhancement of man's thought and rationality, purity, and being; plus the moral uprightness of individuals. A society of moral individuals is already one with a foundation for infrastructural development—involving the provision of amenities, services, and other physical and technological structures for man's use. Whether in human or infrastructural aspects, the overriding aims of development are that: one, to provide citizens with the basic necessities of life (food, shelter, clothing, security, freedom); and, two, to free man from all forms of human misery, ignorance, servitude, and dependence. Hence purposive national development plan must reflect those two ideals—human and material. However, present study shall consider development to mean qualitative and quantitative improvement in all aspects of human endeavor—whether economic, political, cultural, environmental, and/or social. Somehow, these are lacked in Africa.

Underdevelopment

Under-development is adapted include the socio-political and economic quandary, governmental inefficiencies, failures leading to several societal malaises and injustices on the continent of Africa. Under-development is the absence of those indices of development. It could be said that imperialism/colonialism is the cause of underdevelopment in Africa. But it is common knowledge that is not all African states that emerged from colonialism. Similarly, Marxists hold that every state of society is a historical phase in the history of such society. But some societies under capitalism have developed without revolution. Modernization theorists would want us believe that development comes naturally, as a product of handwork, and that traditional social structures, such as kinship, ethnicity, extended family, superstition, hinder it. Yet there still are those who hold that development is a product of historical and political evolution. Thus none of these theories can wholly account for the continuing underdevelopment in Africa indicated in hunger, want, insecurity, and lack of social amenities/infrastructures. Corruption and injustice seem a bane to the achievement of development in Africa. And it has become a crisis.

Agreeably, every people have developed in one way or another to a greater or lesser extent; hence underdevelopment is not merely the absence of development. Underdevelopment only makes sense as a means of comparing levels of development. It is very much tied to the fact that human social development has been uneven and from a strictly economic view-point some human groups have advanced further by producing more and becoming wealthier (Rodney, 1972:21). Underdevelopment can also be explained in terms of relationship of exploitation of

one country by another—implying that underdeveloped states are a product of capitalist, imperialist and colonialist exploitation. Accordingly, Rodney (1972, 22) concludes that “...if underdevelopment were related to anything other than comparing economies, then the most underdeveloped countries in the world would be the USA, which practices external oppression on a massive scale, while internally there is a blend of exploitation, brutality and psychiatric disorder.”

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Generally, a theory is “an idea or belief about something arrived at through assumption and in some cases a set of facts, propositions, or principles analyzed in their relation to one another and used especially in science to explain a phenomena” (Obasi, 2000: 38-39). To have any value, “a theory must explain or suggest ways of explaining why a subject matter has certain characteristics; that is, it must have explanatory, predictive, and problem-solving value and not just an intellectual exercise that simply seek to provide new sets of categories of paradigm(s)” (Obadan, 2012). Therefore, the usefulness of theories in providing us with the context and foundation for our research cannot be overemphasized. Scholars have propounded quite a number of theories in explain socio-economic and political phenomena. However, for the purpose of this work, we adopt the institutional and developing state theories.

Dependency Theory

There are many perspectives on the *Dependency Theory* (DT). For instance, one view (Wikipedia, 2022) considers DT as “the notion that resources flow from a *periphery* of poor and underdeveloped states to a *core* of wealthy states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former”. By and large, the central claim of dependency theorists is that rich countries accumulated their wealth through exploiting poorer countries. This implies that the substance of DT is that underdevelopment is mainly caused by the peripheral position of affected countries in the world economy. Thus the implication of DT is that the people/leadership of less-developed countries may not be blame for the failure of their societies to develop rather, Western/developed nations deliberately failed to develop their oversea less developed countries. The idea of state exploitation was initially established through the institution of colonialism and slavery. But by many states achieving independence mostly in the 20th century, state exploitative exploitation of another/other(s) became achievable through neo-colonialism (web).

Historically, however, DT was first proposed in the late 1950s by the Argentine economist and statesman, Raul Prebisch. But by the nineteen sixties and nineteen seventies, DT had started to enjoy much recognition, patronage, and prominence. In conclusion, DT holds that “the nature of our social formations is dependent on how they are integrated with the world capitalist system” (web). In today's realm, dependency thoughts are still “useful in analyzing the widening inequalities between the poor and rich countries, or in analyzing the divisions within a developed or a developing country context” (web).

In a special way, this work applies the *Institutional Theory* (IT) to underscore the pivotal role of both government and its agencies saddled with the major responsibility of governance and to galvanize grassroots development. The Institutional Theory examines the processes and mechanisms by which structures, schemas, rules, and routines become established as authoritative guidelines for social behavior. It asks how such systems come into existence, how they diffuse, and what role they play in supplying stability and meaning to social behavior. It

also considers how such arrangements deteriorate and collapse, and how their remnants shape successor structures (Scott, 2005). IT assumes that organizational actions are limited by normative regulations (Donaldson, 1995; Krajnovic, 2018), and the room for manoeuvre by individuals is narrowed due to the presence of institutions that impose the *modus operandi* (Scott, 2005). A major argument of the institutional theory is that the behavior and functioning of the organization in the same industry is imposed by the institution, not the market itself (Meyer & Rowan, 1997). According to Sanchawa (2015), IT considers public policy as an output by government institutions as it is authoritatively determined, implemented and enforced by them. Sanchawa explained further that IT draws a very strong relationship between public policy and government institutions because there cannot be a public policy except it is opted, implemented and enforced by some governmental institution(s). In other words, the success (or lack) of public policy objective(s) could be linked to strength or weakness of governmental institutions to effect public policy legitimately—including the legal obligations to command loyalty of the citizens universally, and apply legitimate reprimand for violators.

By this theory, the failure of any government implies the failure of its institutions, agencies, and citizens—which can never assure of development. Accordingly, the theory of the *Developmental State* (DS) is deployed to support the institutional one to properly situate developmental condition of Nigeria (or Africa) vis-à-vis those among some successful states elsewhere around the developed world. Historically, the theory of the DS was first deployed especially in Japan after the devastating destructions of the Second War.

THE DEVELOPMENTAL PROBLEMS IN NIGERIA: A BRIEF HISTORICAL APPROACH

History offers the opportunity to account for a past, understand the present, and project the future. Nigeria's history is replete with myriad problems ranging from palpable economic recession, to political violence and social evils such as corruption and immorality. These have had grave consequences for social justice cum development. It is important to note that precolonial "Nigeria" was a number of "independent" kingdoms, empires and emirates under traditional rulers revered as "semi-divine" and who had powers of life and death on their subjects; powers of taxation, punishment and reward. During that era, justice was seen as the fiat of the ruler. Having amalgamated the North and the South of the colony into a united country in 1914 (despite their apparent and ominous cultural and political experiences), Lord Lugard became Nigeria's first leader (as Governor-General). Well, the antecedents of development had shown a fundamental difference in their respective aspirations. For instance, the south operated a system of political leadership from the grass roots and the people remained the custodian of their own rights before the intrusion of the British. Yet in the North, the Fulani Emirs emerged, as in coup imposed on the people, destroyed the political antecedent of the society with minimum resistance; maintained the interest of the ruling class, selfishly against that of the mass of the people. However, the newly introduced British system of indirect rule paid off in the North; the system permitted the Emir to rule through their family-heads as Chiefs. Thus place of native authority (in the North) marked the emergence of aristocratic political leadership in Nigeria—a condition that has continued to threaten the unity of the country till date.

The 1946 Richard's constitution divided southern Nigeria into West and East, leaving the North intact, with Ibadan, Enugu, and Kaduna as regional centers of power, and Lagos the seat of

colonial authority. Each Region had a Lieutenant Governor, all under the Governor-General in Lagos. This pattern remained until independence in 1960. We must state here that the British arrangement was unjust and marked off ethnic suspicion in Nigeria's political history (Adewale 1981, 20). Political (regional) leaders thus emerged along the lines of constitutional/ethnic demarcations—the ensuing rivalries coupled with corruption culminated in military take-over in 1966. The rage in the then Western house of Assembly, the disaffections of the census and election results and the emergent kidnapping and killing culminated into the Nigeria's first Military coup on January 15, 1966; and a 30-month civil war ensued (the secessionist Biafra surrendered on January 15th, 1970, although the discontent continued in the mind of the defeated East. This condition ignited uneven developmental opportunities in the future country.

Successive military regimes thrived on the Nigerian scene from 1966 (with civilian interregnum between 1979 and 1983) till 1999. Big revenue from oil boom emerged; and engaged in full scale financial proficiency and let go the rare golden opportunity of industrializing Nigeria. Gowon was forcibly succeeded by short-lived Murtala Muhammed and later General Obasanjo who honorably but hurriedly handed back power to civilians in 1979. Unfortunately, the civilians of the second republic were grovelingly corrupt. They killed, stole and looted Nigeria. No wonder the military, hungry for power, had reasons to bounce back on December 31st, 1983. Both Buhari and Idiagbon ruled Nigeria with iron fist and medieval inordinacy between 1983 and 1984 before General Babangida overthrew them in 1985. Although Babangida was also ruthless, he established and funded two political parties for the nations. The ensuing elections of 1993 were perceived to have been won by M.K.O. Abiola but were arbitrarily annulled by Babangida, who soon consequently “stepped aside” for a stooge Chief Shonekan in 1993, who himself was subtly overthrown by Abacha in few months. Abacha's was maximum reign of terror until his mysterious death on June 8, 1998, and under the chaos, General Abubakar Abdusalami emerged as Head of State (Uroh, 1998, 17). However, the situation has degenerated to one of untold crises.

So, historically, the basic issues and problems with the Nigerian political project could be succinctly isolated. A few instances could suffice. The truncated Second Republic did not fare better than the First—since both Shagari and his officials were all soaked in the sea of corruption (Nzeribe, 2017). There were reports of corruption against General Gowon's government in the early 70s (Campbell, 1981); and the so-called 'Cement Armada scandal' marred Gen. Murtala's government (Afolabi, 1993). It is common belief that Generals Babangida and Abacha institutionalized official and popular corruption in Nigeria (Gboyega, 1996; Osaghae, 2002). Ever since, such attitudes sow the seed of underdevelopment. Unfortunately, that seed has thrived most robustly since the Fourth Republic.

Concerning the current conditions in Nigeria (Africa), Uroh (1998) claims it is “...a crisis of development, the problem is necessarily multidimensional...equally socio-cultural as well as moral; is a product of Africa's chequered history.” Perhaps he holds it a crisis because development is “a rise in the standard of living of a people...a progressive elimination of poverty, unemployment, social inequalities, authoritarian political structures....” One may ask, what led to this embarrassing state of affairs? It is arguable that our immediate postindependence leaders did not have long vision for their various states and they simply channeled their energies to the attainment of political independence. This degenerated with the corrupt/immoral character of the hegemonic class and the devastating role of successive military regimes, dictatorship and wars on the continent. Today, individualism and

self-enrichment is the order of the day. According to Claude Ake (2005), "...alienations, resentment, inefficiency, and corruption" are manifestations of underdevelopment. Ake further holds that "all the African countries that are supposed to be sponsoring NEPAD have been adjudged very corrupt by Corruption Perception Index (CPI) survey of 2002, hence Nigeria, Madagascar, Kenya, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Angola are all wallowing in corrupt practices" (Ake, 2005).

A general conception holds that corruption is any act undertaken either to satisfy oneself or a favored candidate, but act which deviates from social norms. It could be in form of bribery, misappropriation, misapplication or misallocation on ethnic or nepotism grounds. It could be planned/institutional; it could be endemic—involving all and sundry; and it could be developmental (that in the guise of performing contract in which the public official indirectly amass wealth to himself). In Nigeria for example, 'blocking' or 'settlement' or '10%' is commonplace. Some of the most indices of corruption include: self-interest, laziness, economic crunch, poverty, unnecessary bottlenecks attached with service rendering, absence of effective monitoring, absence or ineffectiveness of anti-graft agencies, and capitalist ideology. The manifestation of all these is underdevelopment—loss of faith, timidity, criminality, delinquency, deviance, capital flight, inefficiency, lack of infrastructure, instability, and violence. To account for this condition, a number of theories compete.

Alternative Theories of Development and Underdevelopment

A development theory must be one of the (rival and subsidiary) theories that critique, revise, sum and offer broad explanatory frameworks on development (Pieterse, 2009). Thus, a development theory must comprise of *development concept/strategy*. Development theories are often inter-disciplinary and problem-solving oriented. There are many theories of development; let's discuss a few.

Modernization theory emerged in the 1950s as an explanation of how the industrial societies of North America and Western Europe. It developed is one of the theories that explained the pathway to development; it gained fame in the 1950s. The theory posits that societies develop in fairly predictable stages through which they become increasingly complex. Development depends primarily on the importation of technology as well as a number of other political and social changes believed to come about as a result. According to *modernization theories*, endogenous factors (such as tradition, illiteracy, population, agrarian structures, low division of labor, low scale level of communication and infrastructure) are answerable for underdevelopment in the affected countries. However, Rostow (Rostow, 1990) outlines an optimistic scenario by positing five stages of economic development which all societies in one point in time will transcend to realizing development. However its appeal, Modernization theory has been criticized in that it is Eurocentric; that it ignores the fact that development is not a linear process as it claims it to be; and that it ignores the history and culture of different groups of people and society.

Dependency Theory This seeks to explain development and underdevelopment in more rational tones. Dependency is defined as a 'situation in which a certain number of countries have their economy conditioned by the development and expansion of another' (Greig, Hulme and Turner, 2007; Dos Santos, 1978, 544). For instance, Frank (1970) postulates that the underdevelopment of undeveloped countries is an indication of the unequal and unfavourable conditions they found themselves in the world's capitalist system. The dependency theory rejects development argument that any relationship between the traditional and the modern societies would

culminate into mutual benefits or gains. For them, the possibility of peripheral development is hindered by this relationship (Greig, Hulme and Turner, 2007). Frank (1970, 8) illustrates further how poorest countries and most remote part of Latin America had been historically linked to the world capitalist system and how this relationship and contact between tradition and modernity led to underdevelopment. So, in a nutshell, the main thrust of the dependency school of thought in expatiating development and underdevelopment discourse has to do with core-peripheral relationship in the world capitalist system and how the system has a negative repercussion on the periphery states. Thus Frank used the core-periphery nexus to refer to the industrialized/developed and underdeveloped/poor nations respectively.

Alternative Development Theory This perspective emerged in the 1970s and it explains how development can be engineered across space and especially in the underdeveloped part of the world of which Africa continent is an integral part. It is essential to note the fact that, dissatisfaction with mainstream development led to movement of alternative development. By mainstream development is meant the meta-narratives or grand theories to development which include the modernization and dependency schools of thought. Another Alternative view is that development should be geared to the satisfaction of needs, endogenous and self-reliant and in harmony with the environment. Whether this was meant to be an alternative practice of development apart from the main-stream or whether it is to change mainstream development is not quite settled (Pieterse, 1998). Thus the Alternative Development stride is directed to see to the extent local (traditional) and expert (modern) could deploy the bottom up approach with the objectives directed at the provision of basic needs of citizens. A critical question is whether alternative development is an alternative way of achieving development, broadly sharing the same goals as mainstream development but using different means, participatory and people-centered which is conversely to the mainstream development theories which focus on the state as their agent. It would seem this way if we consider the huge increase of development funds being directed through NGOs during the past two decades which now surpass the total annual disbursements through the IMF and World Bank. Despite the new dimension brought on board by the alternative development in the development and underdevelopment discourse with focus on NGOs and local actors as its agents, it is not devoid of censures. For instance, it lacks sufficient theoretical cohesion and there exist varying understandings of what is alternative development and what is not. However, one insight to DT is *neo-liberalism*.

Neo-liberalism This perspective in development theory is the introduction of under the principle of globalization. Neo-liberalism is in the first instance a theory of political economic practices that proposes that human well-being can best be advanced by liberating individual entrepreneurial freedoms and skills within an institutional framework characterized by strong private property rights, free markets and free trade. The role of the state is to create and preserve an institutional framework appropriate to such practices. The state has to guarantee, for example, the quality and integrity of money. It must also set up those military, defense, police and legal structures and functions required to secure private property rights and to guarantee, by force if need be, the proper functioning of markets' (Thorsen and Lie). Neo-liberalism rests on economic liberalization, free trade, open markets, privatization, deregulation and enhancing the role of private sector in society with the minimal role of the state in the economy (for instance, *Structural Adjustment Program* was packaged for the developing countries which several African countries including Nigeria, Ghana, and Zambia keyed into).

Essentially, the Structural Adjustment Program represented the policies implemented by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank (the Bretton Woods Institutions) in

developing countries in the 1980s and 1990s. This policy change were conditions for getting new loans from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) or World Bank, or for obtaining lower interest rates on existing loans following the oil crisis which put burden on most economies especially the developing and the underdeveloped countries. Conditionalities were attached to ensure that the money lent will be spent in accordance with the overall goals of the loan. The Structural Adjustment Programs (SAPs) are created with the goal of reducing the borrowing country's fiscal imbalances. The neo-liberal prescription has been seen as a panacea for spreading growth across space since it is market led but it has been challenged and criticized by many scholars that it brought more inequality across space than ever before; that it failed to restore economic growth in short and medium term run, introduction of SAP led to worse health status of people in countries which implemented SAP and that SAP do not address the economic constraints of Sub-Saharan Africa (low levels of technology, human resource skills, small and fragmented markets).

Eventually, the current state of under-)development (which has been described by scholars as a development crisis) on the African continent cannot be explained away from one perspective alone but several perspectives of exogenous and endogenous factors which have plagued the continent for decades. One of the exogenous causes of African underdevelopment widely alluded to by many scholars in the literature has to do with colonialism. Africa's underdevelopment, from the perspective of exploitation of precious natural resources, could be linked her colonial experience. The system did not just introduce the exploitative capitalist system; it initiated the erosion of basic/enduring African system of values and accountability.

Moreover, indigenous African countries/citizens also played a very weak role in the world capitalist system with focus on production of raw material with less or no value which affects their relationship in the world market. Apart from the exogenous factors accounting for Africa's underdevelopment, there are equally important endogenous factors causing underdevelopment in Africa. One of such endogenous factors is corruption. Today, most African nation-states have been independent for forty years. Unfortunately, at forty, many of these nation states have made either minimal progress or stagnated, in terms of socioeconomic growth and development. Despite the fact that the continent's problems are multifaceted, corruption, particularly in countries where it has become an integral part of the social fabric, is a major handicap to their development efforts. Corruption may be defined simply as the misuse of entrusted power for private gain (Ineke, 2010; Transparency International, 2006).

The financial resource involved in these corrupt deals could have been channeled into useful project that will help to stimulating growth and development in African countries. It is also important to take note of the fact that no single regime or government in Africa after independence has been excluded from corruption saga (as was the case of Ghana and Nigeria, for instance).

One offshoot of the foregoing is the fact that post-independent African nations are replete with weak sociopolitical institutions (besides other legal formations). In some sense, this retrogression could also account for the underdevelopment on the continent; this is also an endogenous factor in explaining the divergence in developed and the less developing and underdeveloped countries. Increasingly research has shown that weak, missing or perverse institutions are the roots of underdevelopment. Other explanations for development, such as technological innovation, investment, or years of schooling are not associated with higher rates of economic growth (Shirley, 2005; Easterly, 2002). The vast majority of Africans today live in

countries that have failed to create or sustain strong institutions to foster exchange and protect persons and property. Most of African countries are suffering from these problems but a point must be made that, there are some countries whose institutions are weaker than others (Sudan, Congo, Somalia, *etcetera*). Individuals in these countries enforce most bargains using informal mechanisms—private armies; threats to reputation; ostracism—and they have little trust. The state is either too weak to prevent theft of property by private actors, or so strong that the state itself threatens property rights and personal independence. Individuals and organizations face a high risk that they will not be able to realize a return if they invest in specific knowledge, skills, or physical assets, so they refrain from investment; production, innovation, and productivity are low and the economy festers (Shirley, 2005). The Nigerian experience in the Fourth Republic is a case in point.

NIGERIA'S 4TH REPUBLIC AND THE CRISIS OF DEVELOPMENT: A CRITICAL OVERVIEW

Nigeria's 4th Republic refers to the period of governance in Nigeria since 1999 on the basis of the democratic tradition. Specifically, *The Fourth (4th) Republic* has had four (4) regimes (Olusegun Obasanjo, Umaru Yar'Adua, Goodluck Jonathan, and Muhammadu Buhari). The main presuppositions in the work are garnered from the activities/developmental efforts or otherwise under those respective regimes. With the 4th republic as a period in Nigeria's modern history, reference, therefore, would be made to certain periods in the past and precursors of this history.

1999 marks the emergence of what is now referred to as *The Fourth (4th) Republic*. From the chaotic political situation, Abubakar organized and handed power to Gen. Obasanjo, though himself a stooge of the Northern oligarchy. Since 1999 may, Obasanjo has been termed a "bridge"¹² by the Northerners. Although he did take some hearty decisions, his tenure as Nigeria's president of the Fourth Republic is threatened by two important developments: how to revive a dead economy, rehabilitate the nation and sustain the nascent democracy, on the one hand; and how to grapple with the states and minorities fight and agitation for resource control—which no previous regime had had any serious consideration for since independence.

Theoretically, the democratic tradition of governance has held sway in Nigeria since 1999 (the Fourth Republic), also in the midst of underdevelopment. Its performances rest wholly on the rare persistency of the democratic tradition (spanning 23 years now) and the fragile national unity maintained thus far. However, to the extent the nation has bestowed the basic ideals of democracy are undetermined. Thus the Nigerian Fourth Republic has been marred with issues about hunger, insecurity, corruption many other infamies.

Official and local reports of corruption in Nigeria's 4th Republic abound in every local Nigerian and (sometimes) international news medium. Amid many other un-apprehended suspects, here are a few:

- a. Former Bayelsa State Governor, Diepreye Alamiyeseigha escapes to UK after EFCC arraigns him for embezzling 55 million dollars (Premium Times, 2016);
- b. Joshua Dariye, former Governor of Plateau State has been accused of (and jailed for) laundering 1.126 billion naira (ecological funds)..having to be pardoned in 2022;

- c. Retiring Army Chief, Tukur Buratai discovered to own Housing Estates in Dubai and other Asian states, and stockpiling of foreign currency in several houses in Abuja; he was rather re-appointed Nigeria's envoy to Benin Republic;
- d. EFCC accused Minister Diezani Alison-Madueke of stealing 47.2 billion naira and 487.5 million dollars in cash and property (www.efcc.govt.ng).

Notably, those issues and attitudes find established catalysts in tendentious party affiliations and constitutions, sponsored banditry/kidnapping—perpetuated by 'god-fatherism' in political succession and arm-twisted judiciary. Consequently, these further sink the country deeper in the shallows of infrastructural decay, lack and social-human under-development.

Corruption appears to be at the bottom of most of Nigerian social infamies. Two explanads contend in the attempt to understand the nature of corruption in contemporary Nigeria. In the first place, there is what is called *institutional failure*—a situation where there is lack of developmental infrastructures not separated from the overbearing influence of the ruling class. Shuaib (2015) refers to such as institutional frailties. In fact, Ake (1985, 4) observes that “in the absence of autonomizing mechanisms in the post-colonial state, the resources of the state become the tools of particular groups, especially the hegemonic factions of the ruling class.:The second explanad is the disjointed idiosyncratic (cultural or ethnic) and behavioral dimensions of Nigerian citizenry and her other segments igniting untold unimaginable immoralities, impunity, and leading to further under-development (Okolo and Akpokhide, 2014)—this point is also validated by the UNODC (2017) report. These two accounts seem to validate Ekeh's (1975) *two publics* theory (civic and primordial). Moreover, both explanads indicate corruption in Nigeria as generic.

A general characterization/feature of contemporary Nigerian (African) politics and society suggests that while the nations of the world are embracing purposeful governance that guarantee development, the political actors of the Nigerian system are also celebrating recourse to legalized embezzlement, pabendalism, ringing; corruption, and other anti-people practices, after all, what can the people do if laws and gods “can understand”? But again, are all these acts or behaviors not against the oath of office at swearing in? Yet once one is not legally culpable, the oath is ineffectual (Asekhauno and Omamor, 2022). This is why Hobbes's *Leviathan* is rather disabling than enabling in considering the people's rights and the terms of the social contract; and even the gods are also disabled since the contract was not binding on them. So, occupants of positions, family heads, community leaders, administrators, teachers, lecturers, and all now operate and behave freely without fear or restraint as if we are back to the Hobbesian *state of nature*; boys and girls now uphold 'next to nudity', and the inordinate pursuit of money, power, and influences, as expedience. The reason is not far-fetched: to satisfy a voracious self and ego and to care for large extended familial/primordial responsibilities (Uroh, 1998). But as ASUU (Academic Staff Union of *Nigerian* Universities) succinctly put it,

It is matter of ordinary human psychology that those who have benefited immensely and who derive political power from fraud are morally, politically and otherwise too weakened and too compromised to deal ruthlessly with corruption. Unfortunately in Nigeria ...compromised leaders determine who is accused and punished and who is not, and this has created severe credibility problems and handicaps in the struggle to defeat the

cancer of corruption... They have made corruption in Nigeria an inevitable feature of the political culture into an art and a political industry. There is abandonment of social welfare by a government that was sworn in to protect the people. Corruption is so systematic that superficial, occasional arrests and dismissals will not make a dent in fighting it. A major problem is that the processes/mechanisms and organs established to address corruption are, themselves, suspects. No public investigation has been established... Public support for any anti-corruption campaign depends on the public perception of the institutions involved and the credibility of such institutions (ASUU, 2005, 2-4).

At the judicial sphere, Judges and Solicitors are no longer harbingers of justice; they have become collaborators and accomplices in crime. To worsen the situation, persons are, on oath, sworn into offices or admitted to the evidence duck, and yet, lie.

Thus in Nigeria, corruption and mal-doing is both ubiquitous and historical; the resultant underdevelopment is also evident and palpable. Regrettably, many attempts have been made to stem the tide and re-direct the trajectory; but such have also proved futile. In fact, Asekhauno (2017) put it thus:

There is copious data/record indicative of Nigeria as one of the world's most corrupt countries; ...and she also has tried to emerge from it. Yet, underdevelopment and degradation thrive everywhere; plundering of public coffers persists; stealing and destruction of state property seem unassailable; the economy is in comatose; there is ignorance amidst increasing school-education; health services remain mere consulting centers; power and other amenities remain epileptic or non-existent, amongst other infamies. Unfortunately, public and private actors (solely or in some connivance) perpetuate the evil corrupt practices. As the tilde needs to be tamed, the national government has instituted some anti-graft agencies; but they have been much of toothless bulldogs.

ESCAPING THE CRISIS OF DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: SOME PRAGMATIC OPTIONS

Africa, like all developing nations, wish to be at par with the developed countries and let us suggest some ways for propelling development on the continent of Africa—with the theory of the developmental state as our guide.

In the first place, traditional culture should be sifted to etch out the useful from the antiquated to match with modernity—education, science and development. Experts have pointed out the place of culture, that it is helpful in understanding economic development. Perhaps the broadest statement comes from the pen of David Landes: Max Weber was right. If we learn anything from the history of economic development, it is that culture makes almost all the difference. Elaborating on Landes's theme, Japanese economist Yoshihara Kunio writes, "One reason Japan developed is that it had a culture suitable for it (Harrison, 2006). It is therefore important on the part of African leaders to focus on their culture in relation to development from economic perspective, Sen's perspective on development, etc. The culture and development nexus brings to mind the Confucian ethics which is a contemporary theory linking economic development to cultures of some countries as a ramification of observation of some countries economic progress since the World War II. Example of such countries includes Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, etc.

Therefore, it is essence on the part of African countries to look inward to their culture in development effort. In fact, there are certain elements of Africa's rich cultural heritage that has led to the evolution and mastery of technical knowledge with respect to the arts, textile industry, craft, music technology and food technology, in which most African societies have made some progress, and have attracted cross-geographic exchange and interaction (Ogungbure, 2011).

Secondly, national citizens/Africans should be encouraged to patronize made in African goods and reduce their taste for foreign goods which is eroding gains that should have been made by African countries should they patronize what is produced in their countries.

Third, emphasis on strong institutions in African countries can be a panacea for African development and not having strong political leaders as it pertains in Africa. This is in tandem with statement by President of USA; Barack Obama when he made a statement that, Africa needs strong institutions and not strong leaders when he met late President Mills of Ghana in 2009. Having a strong institutions can help fight against corruption since the system will be tight to address issues of corruption of whatever form- political corruption which is paramount in Africa as well as corruption in the civil service, etc. In addition, to combat the pernicious problem will require putting in place appropriate anti-corruption and legal machinery; and prosecute without fear and favour. The low incidence of corruption by the governing elites in countries like Denmark, New Zealand, Sweden, Singapore, Finland, Iceland and the Netherland is present, thanks to rational legal bureaucratic practice, is evidence that corruption can be contained (Uneke, 2010). And this cannot be achieved if there exists no strong institutions and therefore, having strong institutions in Africa will be in the right direction toward development.

Fourth, transfer of technology is another pathway which can aid in Africa's development. Technology is basically defines as an application of scientific knowledge to practical problems whilst transfer of technology on the other hand has to do with the processes by which technological knowledge moves within or between organizations and countries; it can be international technology transfer. Technology transfer is an important means by which developing countries can gain access to technologies that are new to them. For example, the acquisition of foreign technologies by East Asian newly industrialized countries, coupled with endogenous technological learning efforts to accumulate the capability to change technologies have been key factors in their rapid technological and economic development. African countries can do the same but definitely there are challenges of acquisition and mastery of technology, both costly and time-consuming, acquired technologies often need to be adapted to local conditions- hence the issue of appropriate technology. All in all, transfer of technology can help African countries in all aspect of their economies toward development

A fifth suggestion is that the government should ensure institutional autonomy and enhanced efficiency of the anti-graft agencies such as ICPC, EFCC, the judiciary, and policing.

The sixth prospect for Nigerian (and indeed, African) development has to do with the government strategically positioning itself in the world capitalist system being perpetuated by globalization and its compelling forces. In order for globalization to have positive impacts on Africa's development, national governments must have the choice to choose among apt monetary, fiscal, trade, macroeconomic and other economic and social policies without heavyhanded intrusion by the developed countries and the multilateral institutions these countries control. In short, a more democratic international economic and political environment is a sine qua non for sustained and broad based economic development to take place in Africa

CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, the development gap between the developed (core) and the underdeveloped (periphery) countries has remained an issue among development experts, academics, politicians and students of development studies. Various development theories of different nature- meta and micro narratives on development have been advanced but the gap between the developed and the underdeveloped countries is widening by days. Various factors have been advanced for African underdevelopment comprising both endogenous and exogenous factors of colonialism and the scramble for African continent, world capitalist, corruption, geographical location and weak institutions. Despite the above causes, there is still hope for Africa's development. Consequently, for Africa (Nigeria) to develop, there is the need: a. To be an emphasis on strong institutions in African countries,

- b. there should be adequate transfer of technology to the continent,
- c. Africans should ensure that they strategically position themselves in the world capitalist system.
- d. In addition, African States should evolve policies that are development oriented. These should aim at reducing poverty and inequality. This is particularly in Africa, where there is no linkage between policy formation and policy implementation.

Finally, and with the dawn of President Tinubu's Administration (May, 2023) as I conclude this paper, there is renewed hope for new/more effective strides in the areas of security, the economy/job creation, agricultural/infrastructural development, amid practical steps to relieve the pains and pangs of poverty and reverse the underdeveloped trajectory in Nigeria.

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